

Spatial proteomics couple to Mass Spectrometry (BioID-MS)

ID: SP0009-A

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Protocol description

BioID (proximity-dependent Biotin Identification) is a method for labeling proteins with biotin in a proximity-dependent manner. Biotinylated proteins can be selectively isolated by affinity purification and identified by nLC-MS/MS. The final output is a proximity proteomic data set.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Co-Isogenic Resolute Cell lines: Jump In™ T-REx™ HEK 293 (Invitrogen™ A15008) over-expressing the bait SLC tagged with BirA lygase at C-term or N-terminal domain. ▪ SH-quant : Isotopic labeled peptide : [NH₂}AADITS(L)YK[COOH] (L): Heavy Leu (13C15N) (+15) (Wepf el al., 2009)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium - high glucose (DMEM) Product: D5796-500mL Manufacturer: SIGMA ▪ Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) Product: S1810-5000 Manufacturer: Biowest ▪ Penicillin-Streptomycin (10,000 U/mL) Product: 15140-122 Manufacturer: Gibco ▪ Blasticidin HCl Product: ant-bl-5b Manufacturer: InvivoGen ▪ G418 disulfate salt (Geneticin) Product: A1720-5G Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich ▪ Doxycycline hyclate: Product: D9891-1G Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich ▪ D-(+)-Biotin, 98+% Product: A14207 Manufacturer: Alfa Aesar ▪ 1X Dulbeccos PBS without Ca & Mg 1x500mLs (Sigma) Product: D8537-500ML Manufacturer:Sigma ▪ HEPES: Product: 9105.3 Manufacturer: Carl Roth ▪ NaCl: Product: s7653-5K Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich

- **Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)**
Product: E6758-500G
Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich
- **Ethyleneglycol bis(2-aminoethyl ether)-N,N,N',N' tetraacetic acid, (EGTA).**
Product: E3889-100G
Manufacturer: Sigma
- **Sodium deoxycholate (DOC)**
Product: 30970-25G
Manufacturer: Sigma
- **Ammonium bicarbonate (ABC)**
Product: 09830
Manufacturer: Sigma
- **KCl**
Product: 9541
Manufacturer: Merk
- **Urea**
Product: 33247
Manufacturer: sigma
- **Sodium lauryl sulfate solution 10% (SDS)**
Product: 71736-500mL
Manufacturer: Merk
- **Trizma® base Primary Standard and Buffer, ≥99.9% (titration), crystalline**
Product: T1503
Manufacturer: Sigma-aldrich
- **Benzonase® nuclease,**
Product: 71205-3
Manufacturer: Merck Millipore (Novagen)
- **Alternative NP-40**
Product: 492016-100 mL
Manufacturer: Merk
- **Protease inhibitor cComplete**
Product: 0505648900
Manufacturer: Roche
- **AC-Leu-Leu-argininal x ½ H₂SO₄**
Product: 11 034 626 001
Manufacturer: Roche
- **Aprotinin from bovine lung**
Product: 10 981 532 001
Manufacturer: Roche

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Trypsin inhibitor from soybean Product: 10 109 886 001 Manufacturer: Roche ▪ StrepTactin Sepharose (50% suspension) Product: 2-1201-010 Manufacturer: IBA ▪ Bio-Rad Protein Assay Dye Reagent Concentrate Product: 5000006 Manufacturer: Bio-Rad ▪ Protein standard I Product: 5000005 Manufacturer: Bio-Rad ▪ DTT (DL-Dithiothreitol), for molecular biology, minimum 99% titration Product: D9779-5G Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich ▪ Iodoacetamide (IAA) Product: I1149-5G Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich ▪ Water, for HPLC LC-MS Grade Product: 83645.320 Manufacturer: VWR ▪ SpeedBeads™ magnetic carboxylate modified particles Product: 45152105050250 Manufacturer: GE Healthcare ▪ SpeedBeads™ magnetic carboxylate modified particles Product: 65152105050250 Manufacturer: GE Healthcare ▪ Acetonitrile for HPLC LC-MS Grade Product: 83640.32 Manufacturer: VWR ▪ Ethanol absolute Product: 1.00983.1000 Manufacturer: MERCK ▪ Empore™ SPE Disks matrix active group C18, diam. 47 mm, pk of 20 Product: 66883-U Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich ▪ Trypsin/Lys-C Mix, Mass spec Grade Product: V5073 Manufacturer: Promega ▪ TFA Uvasol (trifluoroacetic acid) Product: 1.08262.0100 Manufacturer: MERCK
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Equipment:	▪ Branson sonicator.

Reagents setup

- **Stocks:**
 - **100 μ M Biotin (2000x):** Add 24.43 mg of Biotin to 1 mL of DMSO. Pipette up and down, and sonicate for 20-30 sec. Freeze in aliquots at -20°C.
 - **1M TRIS-HCl, pH 7.2 (200 mL):** Add 24.23 g of Trizma® base to 100 mL of H₂O. Adjust to pH 7.2 by adding HCl. Then add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at RT.
 - **750 mM HEPES, pH 8 (100 mL):** Dissolve 17.87 g of HEPES in 50 mL of H₂O, adjust to pH 8 by adding 10N NaOH. Add H₂O until volume is 100 mL. Store at 4°C
 - **5M NaCl (250 mL):** Dissolve 73.05 g of NaCl in 200 mL of H₂O, allow to dissolve with stirring. Then add H₂O until volume is 250 mL. Store at room temperature
 - **0.1 M EDTA, pH8 (200 mL):** Add 5.85 g of EDTA to 100 mL of H₂O. Dissolve the EDTA by adjusting the pH to 8 (adding 10N NaOH under continuous stirring). Add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at room temperature.
 - **0.1 M EGTA, pH8 (200 mL):** Dissolve 7.6 g of EGTA to 100 mL. Dissolve the EGTA by adjusting the pH to 8 (adding 10N NaOH under continuous stirring). Add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at room temperature.
 - **10% w/v Sodium deoxycholate - doc - (100mL):** Dissolve 10 g of doc in 90 mL of H₂O.
 - **Protease Inhibitor (1000x).** Cocktail: 1 μ g/mL Leupeptin, 1 μ g/mL Aprotinin, 10 μ g/mL Trypsin inhibitor in H₂O.
- **RIPA modified lysis buffer:**
 - Composition: 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.2, 150 mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM EGTA, 1% v/v SDS, 1% w/v DOC, 1x Proteinase inhibitor cocktail.
 - For 100mL: 5 ml Tris-HCl pH7.2, 3 mL NaCl, 1 mL NP-40, 1 mL EDTA, 1 mL EGTA, 1 mL SDS, 10 mL 10% doc and 78 mL H₂O.
 - Prepare fresh and place on ice before starting the affinity purification experiment.
- **1M KCl (100 ml):** Dissolve 7.4 g KCl in 50ml of H₂O, allow to dissolve with stirring. Then add H₂O until volume is 250 mL. Store at room temperature.
- **50 mM ABC buffer (50 mL):** Dissolve 0.2 g of ABC in 48 mL of H₂O. Prepare fresh and place on ice before starting the affinity purification experiment.
- **Elution buffer:**
 - Composition: 2M Urea, 50 mM Tris pH 7.5
 - For 10 mL: Dissolve 1.2 g of urea in 8 mL H₂O. Add 500 μ L of 1 M Tris-HCl pH 7.5. Finally add H₂O until a final volume of 10 mL is reached.
 - Prepare fresh and place on ice before starting the affinity purification experiment.
- **Pre-digestion buffer:**
 - Composition: 2M Urea, 50 mM Tris pH 7.5, 1mM DTT, 5 μ g/mL Trypsin
 - For 2 mL: Mix 4 μ L of 500mM DTT, 10 μ L of 1 μ g/ μ L Trypsin and 1.986 mL of elution buffer.

- Prepare fresh and place on ice just before starting pre-digestion step.
- **500mM DTT** (5 mL): Dissolve 0.385 g of DTT in 5 mL of H₂O. Aliquot in 200 µl aliquot and store at -20 °C
- **1M Iodoacetamide (IAA)** (100 µl): Dissolve 0.018 g of IAA in 100 µl of H₂O and vortex vigorously. Prepare fresh immediately before use it and protect from the light.
- **70% v/v EtOH in water** (100 mL): Mix 70 mL of ethanol with 30 mL of H₂O . Store at room temperature.
- **50 mM Tris-HCl, pH8:** (200 mL): Add 1.2114 g of Trizma® base to 100 mL of H₂O. Adjust to pH 8 by adding HCl. Then add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at 4 °C.
- **30% TFA in water** (50 mL): Mix 15 mL of TFA with 35 mL of H₂O. Store at 4°C.
- **1% TFA in water** (50 mL): Mix 166µl of 30% TFA solution with 49.8mL of of H₂O. Store at 4°C.
- **Stage tip solvent:**
 - Composition: 0.4% Formic Acid, 2% TFA.
 - For 100 mL: Mix 97.6 mL H₂O, 2 mL TFA and 400 µL FA. Store at 4°C.
- **Peptide elution solvent:**
 - Composition: 60% Acetonitrile 0.4%TFA
 - For 100 mL: Mix 60 mL acetonitrile, 400 µL FA and 39.6 mL H₂O. Store at 4°C.

Procedure

A. Cell culture and induction (Day 1-9)

1. Cell line selection:
 - Thaw HEK293 Jump-in cell line in 6 well plate and incubate for 24 h in DMEM 10% FBS 1% P/S.
 - Replace growing medium for selection medium (DMEM 10% FBS, 1% P/S + Blasticidin HCl 5 µg/mL, and Geneticine 2 mg/mL).
 - Expand cells on this medium for 6 days. On the last day split cells to 3 x 15 cm dishes. Count cells and seed 15x10⁶ cells / dish (40% confluent).
 - After 24 h of incubation at 37°C, check cell confluency. At least 80% confluent is necessary for doxycycline induction.
2. Doxycycline induction (24h):
 - At 80% confluency replace the medium for doxycycline induction medium (DMEM 10% FBS 1% P/S + 1 µg/mL Dox) and incubate cells for 24 h at 37 °C.

3. Doxycycline washout (12 h) and BirA (12 h) induction:
 - Wash the cells with PBS to remove residual doxycycline. Add growing medium (DMEM 10% FBS 1% P/S) and incubate for 12 h at 37 °C.
 - Replace growing medium for Biotin induction media (DMEM 10% FBS 1% P/S, 50 µM Biotin) and incubate cells 12 h at 37 °C.
4. Cell harvesting and freezing.
 - Carefully wash the cells with PBS to remove residual biotin.
 - Harvest the cells in cold PBS (4 °C) supplemented with protease inhibition cocktail by scraping.
 - Centrifuge 1000 rpm, 4 °C, 5 min.
 - Remove supernatant completely and freeze pellet at -80 °C.

B. Affinity Purification (Pull-down) (Day 10)

1. Cell lysis:
 - Thaw cell pellet on ice for 20 min.
 - Add 1 mL of ice-cold RIPA modified lysis buffer per sample and resuspend the pellet by pipetting up and down.
 - Incubate on ice for 15 min.
 - Add 0.3 µl of Benzonase to each sample, vortex and sonicate samples briefly in a Branson sonicator with microtip (30 s, 0.5 s on/0.5 s off, 20% output).
 - Incubate on ice for 15 min.
 - Centrifuge in tabletop centrifuge 14.000 x g, 4 °C, for 20 min
 - Harvest supernatant and take an aliquot (20 µl) for protein quantification -> Aliquot A1
 - Determine protein concentration of cell lysate by Bradford assay. Total protein concentration should be similar from sample to sample. If it is very different, measure again and normalize.
2. Selective isolation of bait protein on StrepTactin Sepharose beads (affinity purification):
 - Beads conditioning: Add 90 µl of StrepTactin Sepharose bead slurry per sample into a new 1.5 mL tube and wash the beads (2x times): Add 1 mL of ice-cold RIPA modified lysis buffer, mix gentle (avoid pipetting) centrifuge @ 1000 rpm 1 min 4°C and discard supernatant.
 - Add beads to protein lysates mix by shaking and place tubes in a wheel. Let the tube roll for 2h at 4 °C. Note: collect beads with the lysate. **Note:** Use a small volume of cell lysate (i.e., 300 µl) to resuspend beads by pipetting and transfer them into the tube.
3. Beads wash:
 - Discard supernatant and transfer beads to a Bio-Rad mini-columns, let buffer come out of the column. Use 1 mL of ice-cold RIPA modified Lysis buffer to resuspend and transfer the beads
 - Wash beads 2 x 1 mL of ice-cold RIPA modified lysis buffer. Let buffer drop by gravity-flow from the column.
 - Wash 1 x 1 mL of ice-cold 1M KCl. Let buffer drop by gravity-flow from the column.
 - Wash 1 x 1 mL of ice-cold 2M Urea. Let buffer drop by gravity-flow from the column.
 - Wash 3 x 1 mL of ice-cold 50mM ABC. Let buffer drop by gravity-flow from the column.
4. Partial protein digestion and protein Elution:

- Remove completely ABC solvent by centrifugation @ 1000 rpm 1 min 4°C.
- Close columns on the bottom and resuspend beads in 100 µl of pre-digestion buffer.
- Incubate 1 h at 25 °C in a shaker (800 rpm approx.). Note: introduce columns in a 1.5 mL tube to prevent lost of the sample in case of leak.
- Open cap and let eluate into a 1.5 mL tube. Spin columns and tubes 1000 rpm 1 min RT.
- Elute (2x times) with 60µl of elution buffer. Let buffer drop by gravity-flow from the column for approx. 2 mins and then collect it by centrifugation (1000 rpm 2 min RT)
- Combine digest and elution (Final sample volume ~ 220 µL)
Note: After this step eluate can be store at -20 °C until complete protein digestion or can be directly digested.

C. Protein digestion (Day 11)

1. Thaw samples and let them reach Room Temperature.
2. Protein Reduction:
 - Add 1.76 µL 500mM DTT (final concentration DTT approx. 4mM)
 - Vortex and spin each sample
 - Incubate 30 min at 25°C on shaker (~800 rpm)
3. Protein alkylation:
 - Prepare a fresh 1M stock of IAA and add 2.2 µl per sample. (Final IAA concentration 10mM)
 - Homogenize with vortex and incubate 30 min in dark at RT. **Note:** Protect samples from light (IAA is light sensitive)
4. Protein digestion
 - Add 0.5 µg of Trypsin, mix gently and incubate at 25°C over night on a shaker (700 rpm)

D. Stage tip C-18 Solid phase extraction (SPE) of digested peptides (Day 12)

1. Acidify sample:
 - Vortex thoroughly and spin down digested samples by short centrifugation.
 - Add 2 µL 30% TFA. Mix thoroughly and check the acidified samples with pH paper strip using 0.2 µL of sample. pH needs to be 3. Continue adding 30% TFA if necessary, until reach the right pH.
 - Spin down samples with a short centrifugation.
 - Store samples at 4°C
2. Stage tip assembly: (Original Reference: Juri Rappsilber et all, 2003)
 - Place Empore disk flat on a clean hard surface and press a gauge bunt ended syringe needle into the Empore disk to core out a piece of the filter material.
 - Press a second core into the syringe needle for extra loading capacity.
 - Place the needle into a 200 µL pipette tip and push the cored disk pieces into the pipette tip with PEEK or fused silica tubing. Gently pack the material into the end of the pipette tip; a gap of several millimeters should be visible between the disk and the end of the tip.

- Place Stage tips into 2 mL tubes. Use an adaptor to hold the stage tip. The end of the pipette tip should be about 1 cm from the bottom of the tube.

Note: Prepare 2 stage tip per sample

3. Activate and equilibrate C-18 material:

- Activate C-18 material by adding 100 μ L of 100% acetonitrile and centrifuge at 1000-1600 rpm, RT, 1-2 min. Discard flow through. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually. Repeat this step 3 times.
- Equilibrate C-18 material by adding 60 μ L of stage tip buffer and centrifuge at 1000 – 1600 rpm 1-2 min. Discard flow through. Discard flow through. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually. Repeat this step 2 times.

4. Load sample in stage tips:

- Split sample volume in 2 (~110 μ l)
- Load 110 μ l of acidified sample in stage tip, centrifuge at 1000 – 1500 rpm, RT, for 1 – 3 min. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually.
- Collect the flow through, load again the column and repeat the previous step.
- Transfer flow-through into empty brown glass vial. For later QC.

5. Wash:

- Wash sample loaded onto SPE column with 100 μ L 0.1% TFA and centrifuge at 1000 – 1500 rpm., RT, for 1 – 3 min. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually.
- Discard flow through

6. Peptide Elution:

- Elute with 2 \times 50 μ L elution buffer in a 1.5 mL low binding tube.
- Evaporate solvent in a vacuum centrifuge at 45 $^{\circ}$ C until 2 μ L remain. Check regularly and ensure that samples are not dried to completeness! Note: Peptides can be store dry at -20 $^{\circ}$ C until MS analysis.

7. Peptide reconstitution

- Before MS analysis reconstitute samples in 32 μ L of 0.1% TFA 16.66 fmol/ μ l SH-quant isotopic label peptide, mix by vortex
- Spin down samples and sonicate for 10 min in a sonicator bath
- Centrifuge (14.000 rpm., 4 $^{\circ}$ C, 15 min)
- Transfer supernatant to a glass vial with insert.
- Samples are now ready for MS analysis. They can be directly injected in a MS device or store at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.

Additional notes

- Section: Reagent set up:
 - The volumes shown in this section are indicative. The required volume of each reagent will depend on the number of samples to be prepared.

- Always use LC-MS grade water for the preparation of all the solvents and Buffers.
- Use only glass tips for handling TFA and FA.
- Section: SP3 digestion of proteins. Step 4. → Magnetic beads stock can be prepared in higher volume and store in at 4°C until use.

Data availability

References

- Wepf, A., Glatter, T., Schmidt, A., Aebersold, R. & Gstaiger, M. Quantitative interaction proteomics using mass spectrometry. *Nat. Methods* 6, 203–205 (2009).
- Juri Rappsilber, Yasushi Ishihama and Matthias Mann, 2003. **Stop And Go Extraction Tips** for Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization, Nanoelectrospray, and LC/MS Sample Pretreatment in Proteomics. *Anal. Chem.* 75, 663-670.
- Christopher S Hughes, Sophie Moggridge, Torsten Müller, Poul H Sorensen, Gregg B Morin, Jeroen Krijgsveld. Single-pot, solid-phase-enhanced sample preparation for proteomics experiments. *Nat Protoc* 2019 Jan;14(1):68-85. doi: 10.1038/s41596-018-0082-x.

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